

Citation for the Presentation of the
2012 ICPE Medal to

Professor Edward F. (Joe) Redish,
University of Maryland, USA

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Edward Frederick Redish, known throughout the Educational Physics community as Joe Redish, is Professor of Physics at the University of Maryland. He is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2012 in recognition of his profound and wide-ranging contributions to Physics Education Research, that have powerfully influenced the development of the field in the USA and many other countries throughout the world.

Joe Redish graduated from Princeton University in 1963 with a Magna Cum Laude degree in Physics. He then went on to earn a PhD in theoretical nuclear physics from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1968. Dr. Redish immediately became a member of the faculty at the University of Maryland, becoming a full Professor in 1979 and Chairing the Department of Physics and Astronomy from 1982 to 1985. He first became actively involved in the field of physics education research in 1982 and subsequently he has made physics education the primary focus of his research.

Although Professor Redish's research is multi-faceted, he has concentrated on the use of computers in education. He was founder and co-principal investigator of the Maryland University Project in Physics Education and Technology (M.U.P.P.E.T.) and the Comprehensive Unified Physics Learning Environment (CUPLE). With various co-authors has contributed to the publication of innovative curricular materials through works such as Understanding Physics and the University of Maryland Tutorials in Physics Sensemaking. In 2003 he inspired many colleagues to use physics education research based teaching methods through his book Teaching Physics with the Physics Suite. His current interests include cognitive linguistics in Physics Education Research, the integration of mathematics and physics in advanced classes, and catalyzing related reforms in biology education.

Professor Redish has received many prestigious awards, including the 1998 Robert A. Millikan Award of the American Association of Physics Teachers, and a National Science Foundation Director's Award as a Distinguished Teaching Scholar in 2005. Today the International Commission on Physics Education takes great pleasure in further recognizing his work, and his many achievements, by awarding him the 2012 ICPE Medal for outstanding contributions to international physics education.

Robert Lambourne
Chairman of ICPE